

**ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ВОСТОЧНЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ СЕГОДНЯ:
КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ НАПРАВЛЕННОСТЬ ОБУЧЕНИЯ**

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Аннотация. *Коммуникативный подход направлен на создание психологической и языковой готовности к общению: необходимо, чтобы студент сознательно осмысливал материал, моделировал общение и способы взаимодействия. Данный подход позволяет заинтересовать студентов изучать иностранный язык посредством накопления и расширения знаний и опыта. В статье освещается проблема несоответствия целей и задач методики преподавания восточных языков нуждам учащихся, а также рассматривается возможность переосмысления принципа коммуникативной направленности обучения для разрешения данной проблемы.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативное обучение, востоковедение, восточные языки, принципы обучения, методика преподавания, система обучения, лингводидактика, принципы коммуникативности.*

**TEACHING EASTERN LANGUAGES TODAY:
COMMUNICATIVE DIRECTION OF LEARNING**

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Annotation. *The communicative approach is aimed at creating psychological and linguistic readiness for communication: it is necessary that the student consciously comprehend the material, model communication and ways of interaction. This approach allows students to be interested in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and expansion of knowledge and experience. The article highlights the problem of inconsistency between the goals and objectives of the*

methodology of teaching Eastern languages to the needs of learners, as well as considering the possibility of rethinking the principle communicative orientation of training to solve this problem.

Keywords: *communicative learning, oriental studies, eastern languages, principles of learning, methods of teaching, learning system, linguodidactics, principles of communicativeness.*

INTRODUCTION

The study of Eastern languages in Kazakhstan has gained wide popularity, caused not only by the strengthening of political and economic ties with the Asian region, but also by the rapid influx of modern Eastern culture, which also includes movies, music, video games, fashion, and more. Now there is almost a whole generation of young people listening to Korean popular music, watching Asian TV series, and playing Japanese video games. Such a mass enthusiasm for the products of Asian culture inevitably causes an increased interest in the study of Eastern languages.

In such circumstances, it became necessary to rethink the goals, objectives and approaches to teaching the languages of Asia. This article discusses the possibility of rethinking the communicative orientation of education as the main principle of the methodology of teaching the eastern language. The traditional domestic method of teaching oriental languages originates from the development of oriental studies. For several decades, these two areas have been merged together, having a common goal - training specialists in the countries of Asia and Africa, including history, language, literature, economics, politics and other aspects. Thus, the eastern language was taught mainly as a means of knowing the entire body of knowledge about the region. The characteristic features of this technique include the use of historically significant texts and documents, the emphasis on the formation of translation skills, special attention to the accuracy of conveying the meaning of linguistic forms, the predominance of writing and reading exercises. Analysis of literary works, knowledge about the historical development of the language, the ability to connect the language with the culture, history, economy of the country, simultaneous and consecutive translation - this is not a complete list of knowledge and skills of an orientalist.

However, in the last few years there has been an increase in the popularity of Oriental languages outside of Oriental studies as a science. A huge number of young people want to learn an oriental language because they want to listen to music, watch movies and anime, read manga in the original language. For these students, the main purpose of learning is live communication, they do not need to be able to correctly translate texts, know the history of the country being studied and read complex documents. However, many of them choose oriental studies faculties and specialties, because this is often the only place where they have the opportunity to study these languages. Today, numerous language schools and courses are being opened, as well as additional departments at the faculties of foreign languages, but all of them are often based on a proven "Eastern" teaching methodology. Thus, a change in the trend in language learning will inevitably lead to the need for changes in the methodology of its teaching, to the development of new goals and objectives of learning that correspond to the goals and objectives of students.

In other words, in addition to the classical Eastern methods of teaching the Eastern language, there is a need to develop methods for a wider range of students - non-specialists. To resolve the above problem, it is most appropriate to turn to linguodidactics as a science that studies the general patterns of language learning [4].

In the history of teaching foreign languages, one can trace the predominance of Western languages as objects of research, since in secondary and higher English, German, French were predominantly studied in our educational institutions. In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of Eastern languages at language faculties, which is undoubtedly associated with an increased interest in the Asia-Pacific region, i.e. it can be argued that the theory and methodology of

teaching Eastern languages can and even should borrow the basic concepts and definitions, as well as theoretical and methodological issues of private linguodidactics.

Active learning methods are activities that require a creative approach to the material and create optimal conditions for independent work: role-playing, business games, various types of discussions, creative projects, work with sources. The use of such teaching technologies in classes as designing, organizing role-playing communication and preparing presentations shows their effectiveness, helps creative processing of learned material with a personal and active orientation of the learning process. These techniques contribute not only to mastering the system of linguistic knowledge and the laws of functioning of the language being studied, its functional varieties, the development of computer skills, receiving, analyzing and processing information from the global network, but also the development of the personality of the student, the disclosure of his creative abilities, independent thinking. The teacher needs to create conditions for practical language acquisition for each student, to choose such teaching methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity, to intensify cognitive activity in the process of teaching Chinese. Modern pedagogical technologies - such as collaborative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources - help to implement a student-centered approach to learning, provide individualization and differentiation of learning, taking into account the abilities of students.

The communicative approach is aimed at creating a psychological and linguistic readiness for communication: it is necessary that the student consciously comprehend the material, model communication and ways of interaction. Students show excellent results when using multimedia aids, programs and the Internet in a communicative approach. This approach allows students to be interested in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and expansion of knowledge and experience.

The principle of communication in teaching foreign languages. In this paper, as a way to solve the problem of developing a new methodology for teaching the Japanese language, we consider the rethinking of one of the principles of learning a foreign language - the principle of communicative orientation (principle of communicativeness).

This principle is determined by the practical orientation of knowledge, the organization of training in a natural environment or as close as possible to it using language learning [1; 4], i.e. the learning process approaches the process of real communication, where the main goal is to master the language as a means of communication.

There are several features of the principle of communicativeness: the internal motivation of the student's speech actions, their purposefulness, the personal meaning of communication, individuality as the student's right to express his point of view in the classroom, speech and thought activity when performing exercises as opposed to memorization and imitation, interaction and contact of students with each other and with the teacher, the situational nature of statements, the information content of teaching, its novelty for students, heuristics as a creative nature of teaching, the functionality of speech and the problematic nature of the learning material [3].

The formation of strategic competence implies the ability to use adequate situations of communication, verbal and non-verbal communication strategies (a set of speech means and speech techniques to achieve the intended goal of communication) for the purpose of effective intercultural communication with a lack of language means; the ability to understand someone's statement and generate verbal statements, first of all, in those cases when certain difficulties arise in the process of oral communication. In the domestic methodology, strategic competence is considered as compensatory competence.

The study of the strategies of communicative behavior of representatives of a different society, their linguo-socio-psychological and cultural characteristics contributes to the

familiarization of "non-native speakers" of the language with the value orientations of native speakers of this language, the convergence of intercultural distance between representatives of different societies and, ultimately, the formation of a linguistic personality who owns the basics of intercultural communication, educating her readiness to adapt to the culture of another nation, a different socio-cultural context of interaction and influence in order to develop an optimal strategy for communicating in a foreign language.

In practice, this principle develops into a learning system where live communication is at the heart of the lesson, the interests of students are taken into account, role-playing games, project tasks involving joint new solution of problems and problem situations. Not language exercises are used, but conditional speech exercises, where the speaker has a specific speech task, for the solution of which one or another statement must be used. The content of training does not come down to the formation of individual lexical, grammatical and other skills, but to certain communication skills, for example, to get to know each other, to tell about yourself, to ask for advice. At the same time, individual lexical, grammatical and other skills are formed as a secondary and at the same time a basic component necessary for successful communication.

The practical use of the language is not only the goal of learning, but also a means to achieve this goal [2]. The principle of communication in teaching oriental languages. The above-mentioned classical oriental education involves not only teaching the oriental language, but also knowledge about the region, its culture, literature, politics, history, economics, etc. For many years, the main content of Oriental studies was the translation and commentary of original sources, and this left a deep imprint on the nature of language learning.

As in any other methodology, learning objectives determine the methods and means used in language classes. In the case of classical oriental studies, the focus on a competent, clear presentation of the content of the text, the accuracy of translation and small nuances lead to voluminous translation tasks, written exercises, clear knowledge of grammatical structures. The need to understand the historical, political and other contexts of a given region leads to the corresponding orientation of texts, materials for language classes. It is forbidden argue that live communication and the practical use of language do not play a major role in oriental education, but this is only one of the necessary skills and abilities in the totality of all the knowledge of an orientalist specialist.

A new wave of interest in the East and a huge number of people who want to study Oriental languages outside of Oriental education have led to the need to rethink the process of teaching Oriental languages. This article discusses the possibility of applying the principle of communicativeness that already exists in the teaching methodology as the main principle of teaching students in conditions where students are not specialists in oriental studies. As described above, communicativeness comes down to some characteristics of the educational process that is quite possible to apply to the teaching of Oriental languages. In practice, a communicative orientation can be achieved based on the following characteristics. The motivation of the student and each statement. The lack of motivation negatively affects the learning process, so it is necessary that students are interested in the process, and that each speech exercise makes sense and interest to the speaker. To increase motivation, it is necessary to carefully select the selection of material for training that corresponds to the goals of students, their interests, age group. If it is important for an orientalist to be able to read texts of a political and economic nature, then for a “wider” audience these materials will be inappropriate. The selection of material can also be adjusted in the learning process, involving the students themselves, which may have a positive effect on their attitude to learning.

Purposefulness of training. All training should be directed towards a common goal - mastering the language as a means of communication, while any exercise and any activity during

the lesson should also have the so-called small goals that, taken together, lead to the achievement of a common goal. In other words, if the particular goal of this lesson is “to learn how to talk about yourself, your family, and also learn about the interlocutor,” then the entire set of exercises and tasks should be aimed at achieving this goal. At the same time, it is necessary not to memorize the grammatical rule by substituting incoherent lexical elements, but the parallel introduction of grammatical material necessary to achieve a small goal. In the above case, this may be a system of personal pronouns, verbs in the present and past tenses, a system of adjectives and their agreement with nouns and other grammatical constructions necessary to describe oneself and one's family. Speech-thinking activity allows the student to solve an individual problem. To do this, he needs to be involved in the learning process, communicate with the teacher or other students using a foreign language. To implement this component, it is necessary to work out various types of exercises aimed at involving students in the process, using their personal experience, opinions, and views. Role-playing games are good for this, when students play a certain situation using language means. Various tasks (tasks) involving teamwork, projects, jigsaw tasks also require individual verbal-thinking activity from students.

The personal meaning of communication for the student and individuality as his right to express his point of view in the classroom. These characteristics are closely related to the speech-thinking activity described earlier. Interaction and contact of students with each other and with the teacher. Often a foreign language lesson is a one-way relationship, when the teacher “gives” the material, and the students listen and complete the tasks. Real communication, if present, is only in limited forms: how to “ask a question”, “answer a question”, “repeat”. However, the presence in the classroom of other participants, including the teacher, is in itself a real environment for communication that can and should be used effectively.

Even simply grouping students into small groups to complete an assignment will require them to communicate with each other. For many, it is quite natural that the teacher is always in his “special” place, as if towering in front of the class, however, this automatically pits him against the entire audience, hinders trusting bilateral relations. The position of the teacher as an “insider”, or an equal participant in the learning process, is necessary for a communicative approach. Situation and functionality of statements. The correlation of each specific utterance with a particular communication situation must be maintained throughout the entire learning process. The use of linguistic means outside situations should be minimized, and each grammatical construction or rule is studied in relation to its function and simultaneously with its use in real speech. The selection of grammatical and lexical material, the order of its implementation is also determined by its functions in real communication, and not according to the rule “from simple to complex”.

Informative learning, its novelty for students is achieved by selecting materials that are interesting for students, as well as appropriate for their age, gender, abilities and other individual characteristics.

Heuristic as a creative nature of learning, suggesting spontaneity of statements, rather than prepared and memorized phrases. The problematic nature of learning also plays an important role in the development of logical, creative thinking of students, including them in the learning process. For this, it is necessary to state the problem in the classroom, to involve students in the process of solving this problem using the means of a foreign language available to them.

Analyzing the use of the communicative method in classes, we can confidently note:

- motivation and development of the student's personality, his creative and intellectual potential;

– improving the quality of education;

– interest in learning, activation of creative thinking;

- the desire for research activities, independent work;

- development of information, social and communicative competence of students;
- development of skills for working on design and research assignments;
- satisfaction of students from the results of educational activities;
- the desire of students to participate in research and creative projects.

CONCLUSION

Thus, this article draws attention to the problem of differentiating the processes of teaching an oriental language in accordance with the goals of students. If we are not talking about training specialists in oriental studies, but about teaching an oriental language as a foreign language in non-philological specialties, language courses, additional departments and in language schools, where the main goal of education is the practical use of the language in real communication, it is considered appropriate to strengthen the communicative orientation of education. Historically, the principle of communication has been developed and methodically tested mainly in relation to teaching Western languages, however, it can and should be rethought and more effectively used in the methodology teaching eastern languages.

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